

Regional Characterisation of the Green Energy Transition Potential in North and West Africa Based on the PESTEL Model and Spatial Clustering

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Summary

This paper aims to analyse the regional and country-level characteristics that may influence the energy mix and green energy development opportunities in each country in North and West Africa. The analysis is based on the PESTEL framework, which produces country energy profiles characterised by political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal factors. All the countries in the study area are grouped into three regions/clusters using principal component analysis and *k*-means clustering. The countries in each cluster have similar PESTEL profiles, which provide information to help decision makers gauge the future green energy development opportunities and potentials in this region.

KEYWORDS: Energy transition, regional characterisation, PESTEL model, principal component analysis, *k*-means clustering

1. Introduction

Much attention has been drawn to achieving a Net-Zero future with an increasing number of countries showing commitments to green energy transition (IRENA, 2021). Net-Zero goals require global-level efforts. It is important that underdeveloped regions participate in this energy transition. This paper focuses on North and West Africa. North African countries are blessed with abundant renewable energy resources, and rich in fossil fuels. Countries in West Africa are facing challenges posed by their low access to electricity and high population growth (Alfaro and Miller, 2014).

About 90% of the electricity production is powered by fossil fuels in North and West Africa, compared with the global average of over 60%. Several studies modelled the future of Africa's energy capacity and suggested a "greener" energy mix future in Africa (Alova et al., 2021; Cozzi et al., 2020). In this research, we examined the Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal (PESTEL) aspects of the countries in North and West Africa in order to gain insights into their green energy transition potentials. The results were then used to build country profiles, based on which we assessed regional characteristics of energy mix through grouping the countries with similar profiles using the principal component analysis (PCA) and *k*-means.

2. Methodology

2.1. PESTEL framework

PESTEL is a framework for analysing and monitoring the macro-environmental factors that may have

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a profound impact on an organisation's performance (van der Zwaan et al., 2018). The framework categorises the six forces of politics, economics, socio-culture, technology, environment and law, which characterise the existing conditions in the business environment for energy transition. In this research, data were gathered from various sources (including Africa Energy Database, World Bank, Global Solar and Wind Atlases, United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change and other existing literature) based on the framework to produce profiles of each country in North and West Africa, providing information on the PESTEL conditions in each country to gauge green energy development opportunities in this region. The following factors were selected to represent these conditions: political stability and absence of violence (PSAV), control of corruption (CC), population (POP), population growth (PG), access to electricity (AE), GDP per capita, percentage of official development assistance in gross national income (ODA), GINI coefficient, global innovation index (GII), wind power density (WP1), direct normal solar irradiance (Solar), gross theoretical hydropower potential (Hydro) and NDC (nationally determined contributions) targets (Goal). Based on the current literature, these factors are considered to be good predictors of the future of Africa's energy mix.

2.2. Principal component analysis

PCA is used to reduce multidimensional data to two or three dimensions, by transforming a large set of variables into a small set of principal components (PCs). The first PC (PC1) accounts for the largest possible variance in the dataset. The second PC (PC2) accounts for the next highest variance, and so on. PCA calculates factor loadings, which represent how much each of the original variables contributes to a particular PC. PCA was used to derive PCs that can explain most of the variations in the country profiles. These PCs were then used as variables by *k*-means to group the countries into clusters with similar profiles.

2.3. *k*-means clustering

k-means divides a set of *n* observations into *k* clusters/groups so that the observations within each group are more comparable to one another and different from the observations within the other groups. It does so by minimising within-cluster variances through an iterative process. It first randomly selects *k* observations from the dataset and uses these as the initial means (cluster centres), which are used as the beginning points for every cluster, and then performs repetitive calculations to optimise the positions of the cluster centres. The technique is used to group the countries based on how similar and different their PESTEL profiles are.

3. Results

3.1. Principal components

The first three PCs explain 71.9% of the variances in the country profiles, with PC1 accounting for 32.4%, PC2 23.5% and PC3 16%. According to Table 1, PC1 is characterised by economic factors including GDP, AE, and ODA. PC2 is leaning more towards the political and legal aspects, as PSAV, CC and Goal are the main drivers. Although PC3 is not as pronounced, it brought the social and environmental aspects.

Table 1 Factor loadings of PESTEL variables

Variables	PESTEL	PC1	PC2	PC3
PSAV	Political	10	2	11
CC		13	1	13
GDP	Economic	1	13	12
ODA		3	12	6
GINI		7	5	5
Pop	Social	9	8	1
PG		5	9	9
AE		2	7	10
GII	Technological	8	6	4
WP1	Environmental	4	11	8
Solar		6	10	3
Hydro		12	4	2
Goal	Legal	11	3	7

3.2. Country clusters

Three clusters of countries were identified by *k*-means based on the PCs. As shown in **Figure 1**, the pink cluster includes Egy(Egypt), Libya, Alg(Algeria), Sud(Sudan), and Nigeria, and the green cluster consists of Tun(Tunisia), Mor(Morocco), Cap(Cape Verde) and Gha(Ghana). The blue cluster includes Mau(Mauritania), Sen(Senegal), Niger, Gam(Gambia), Libe(Liberia), Cot(Cote d'Ivoire), Mali, Gui(Guinea), GuiB(Guinea-Bissau), Bur(Burkina Faso), Tog(Togo), Ben(Benin) and Sie(Sierra Leone).

Figure 1 Three country-clusters (Dim1–PC1; Dim2–PC2)

4. Discussion

By the green energy transition potential of a cluster, we mean the market demand decided by the

socioeconomic aspects of a cluster and the natural endowments. Technological aspects can affect the potential of a country to an extent, though fairly marginal as many countries of interest require international help with the energy transition. Having high PSAV and CC can minimise the risk of rapid and frequent changes of policies and the governing regime, so that the countries can work towards their goals detailed in their NDCs.

PCA and *k*-means helped with grouping countries with similar profiles together as shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2 Map of country clusters

The pink cluster has the smallest GHG emission reduction goal and the highest risk of political instability. Nonetheless, this cluster has great potential for green energy transition, given the strong socioeconomic variables. It has the largest total population, the second-highest population growth rate and a huge energy demand gap now and in the future. The countries in the cluster are blessed with prodigious renewable energy resources. Solar and hydropower are ranked the first while wind is the second among the three clusters. These countries are to be a huge market yet to be fully explored. However, the low national commitment is an obstacle for them to unleash their full green energy potential and transit to a high-potential energy market. Therefore, the countries in the cluster have high potential but a low commitment to the green energy transition.

The countries in the green cluster show the highest level of commitment to combat GHG emissions and climate change, along with the highest PSAV and CC compared to the other two clusters. Although the economy is not as strong as the pink cluster, this cluster has the highest AE, the fundamental infrastructure for green energy transition and the lowest population growth rate. These countries also have the highest wind power density and the second-highest solar irradiance for solar power. They are a good choice for international companies to invest in, given the healthy political environment and great renewable energy source potential. These countries have high potential and high commitment to the green energy transition.

The countries in the blue cluster are relatively underdeveloped economically. Politically, they are the middle ground, the same as its goal of 15% GHG emission reduction. The cluster has the smallest total population, but the highest population growth rate. Therefore, the energy production is not meeting the current demand. This cluster has the lowest green energy potentials. While they are not as “gifted” naturally, they have a high level of willingness to engage in the green energy transition. Thus, these countries have generally low potential but a high commitment to the green energy transition.

5. Conclusions

This research produced contextual information about the existing conditions in the business environment for energy transition in North and West Africa. It can be used to assist an organisation in recognising and thereby capitalising on opportunities for green energy development, and it can also be used for identifying current or possible future challenges in energy transition in the region, allowing for effective planning of how to best manage these challenges.

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Biographies

Xuan Zhu is a senior lecturer of GIS and Remote Sensing in Monash University. He received his PhD from the University of Edinburgh and has over 30 years of international experience in GIS and remote sensing, and their applications in environmental and regional resource use planning.

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